

A REVIEW ON IDENTIFYING THE TUMOR MICROENVIRONMENT THROUGH SPATIAL TRANSCRIPTOMICS: INSIGHTS, CHALLENGES, APPLICATIONS AND ADVANCEMENTS

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ABSTRACT

As a tumor develops, the cancer cells come into contact with different types of normal cells (non-cancer cells), but it's not obvious how tumours change to fit in with these new surroundings. Tumor microenvironment describes about what type of cells presents near and surrounding the tumor. The tumor microenvironment consists of structural components, such as the extracellular matrix, together with various supportive cell types. These include stromal fibroblasts, fat cells, endothelial cells, and a wide range of immune populations, for example T and B lymphocytes, natural killer cells, dendritic cells, macrophages, myeloid-derived suppressor cells, and lymphatic cells. The tumour microenvironment (TME) influences metastasis and responsiveness to treatment, making it a crucial component of cancer progression. The tumour microenvironment (TME) can be better understood with spatial transcriptomics (ST). ST makes it possible to

quantify and visualize the gene expression patterns that are present within the spatial context

of tissues, especially cancer cells and the environment. As the traditional single cell sequencing (scRNA) technique that is next generation sequencing (NGS) profiling is based on bulk approaches that lack spatial context. We can now obtain spatial information by capturing tumour diversity and multifocality. By using the ST we can plan the cancer treatment, prevent the cancer progression and drug resistance. This article explains about the techniques that are used in identifying the TME, insights, challenges and their applications in the cancer.

KEYWORDS: Spatial transcriptomics, oncology, tumor, TME, scRNA sequencing, gene expression profiling, tumor heterogeneity, immune microenvironment, cancer therapeutics.

INTRODUCTION

Cancer is the world's 2nd prevalent cause of death, contributing to roughly one out of every 6 fatalities. By 2040, the incidence of cancer cases around the world is anticipated to rise to 27.5 million, which is 62% more than in 2018.^[1] The tumor consists of an ecosystem similar to our healthy organs and tissues, where it helps in existence of cancer cells. This ecosystem is called tumor microenvironment.^[2] As cancer cells multiply, the tumor meets various non-cancerous cells. These cells constitute the tumor microenvironment.^[3] A tumor microenvironment (TME) has an important role in its physiology, structure and function as it provides a supporting environment for malignant activity and influences the responsiveness to the treatment making it an important factor in cancer progression.^[4,5]

Conventional methods such as single-cell RNA sequencing, fails to capture the spatial architecture of tissues due to the destruction of spatial information during the isolation of single cells.^[6] This challenge is addressed by the spatial transcriptomics and can obtain the spatial information.^[6,7]

Components of TME

The tumor microenvironment consists of tumor cells, immune cells, mesenchymal stromal cells and extracellular matrix (ECM).^[8] The immune cells consist of lymphocytes, NK, granulocytes, macrophages, fibroblasts, adipocytes, endothelial cells.^[9,10,11] They engage in a range of immunological activities and responses, including inflammatory reactions that the tumour regulates for survival. Glycoproteins, collagens, and enzymes are among the macromolecules that constitutes the extracellular matrix (ECM), which supports the body's

biomechanical processes.^[10] Endothelial cells release adhesion molecules and cytokines helps in tumor progression and metastasis.^[11]

Importance of TME

TME increases the tumor development by

- i. Changing the environment by producing cytokines promotes tumor growth,
- ii. Presence of dysfunctional immune cells,
- iii. Interaction between tumor and stromal cells increases cancer cell survival, development and metastasis.^[12]

How Tumor heterogeneity changes the TME

Tumours are consists of several types of cancer cells (known as tumour heterogeneity). Tumour heterogeneity refers to the cellular population variability that exists between tumours of the same type in different ill persons (intertumor heterogeneity) or even within a single tumour. The variations between cancer cells (tumor heterogeneity) can alter the tumour environment (TME) and results in developing drug resistance by

- i. Changing the signals between the cytosomes and exosomes which makes it harder for drugs to show its action
- ii. Promoting the release of immunosuppressors like TGF-beta that protects the tumor,
- iii. TME becomes dense which makes it difficult to reach all parts of tumor
- iv. Presence of stem cells in TME which cannot be removed by treatment.^[13]

Spatial Transcriptomics

Spatial transcriptomics refers to a collection of methods that integrate large-scale gene expression analysis with the ability to map these signals to their exact locations within intact tissue sections. Unlike bulk or single-cell RNA sequencing, which loses the spatial organization of cells where ST is associated with all the characteristics of a cell cycle which includes cytotogenesis differentiation, function and death.^[14] ST preserves where transcripts originate, typically at single-cell or subcellular resolution.^[7] This allows researchers to link gene expression patterns to tissue architecture, cellular neighbourhoods, and functional cell interactions within their natural biological context.^[15]

Spatial Transcriptomics Techniques

To study mRNA expression in tissue sections, a number of approaches have been developed in recent years for transcriptome profiling that preserves spatial information.^[16,17] ST methods

address several aspects as follows: number of detected genes, resolution and whole transcriptome analysis and are classified into four subcategories:

- a. Sequence based methods
- b. Probe-based methods
- c. Imaging based methods
- d. image-guided, ST single cell RNA sequencing techniques

a. Sequence based methods

Also, known as next-generation sequencing methods which are unbiased because they are similar to single-cell total transcriptome profiling, which captures polyadenylated RNA transcripts and allows for the discovery of new differential genes or biological pathways. They utilize barcoded sequences (slides or beads). Sequencing-based spatial transcriptomic technology includes tools like 10X Genomics Visium, Slide-sequencing, Stereo-sequencing, and Light-sequencing.^[18]

b. Probe-based methods

Unlike NGS-based spatial transcriptomic techniques, oligonucleotide probe-based technologies, like NanoString's digital spatial profiling system, are designed to collect targeted transcripts in manually selected ROIs. Target transcripts are bound to complementary probes that carry unique oligonucleotide barcodes, which enables their distinction and subsequent separation during analysis. GeoMx DSP, HybISS, and Molecular Cartography are the examples.^[18]

c. Imaging based methods

Imaging technologies are based on a technique known as single-molecule fluorescence in situ hybridisation (smFISH). These approaches are capable of finding up to 6,000 RNA transcripts in a single experiment by repeating the probe binding and imaging steps. This is how it works.

- i. Primary probes bind to specific RNA molecules.
- ii. Then, secondary probes having fluorescent markers attaches to the primary probes.
- iii. Fluorescence signals are captured by imaging the tissue during each cycle.

By continuing this process and evaluating the light signals, we can determine where each RNA is placed in the tissue and how much of it is present.^[19]

d. Image-guided, ST single cell RNA sequencing techniques

Image-guided spatially resolved scRNAseq approaches can pick spatially diverse cells or regions of interest, followed by scRNAseq, keeping their natural spatial information while allowing for in-depth scRNAseq profiling. Geo-seq uses both LCM and scRNA to analyze spatial transcriptome. NICHE-seq utilize fluorescence.^[18]

Table 1: Different ST methods.

ST method	Example	Resolution	Characteristics
Sequence based methods	10x Genomics Visium, Slide-seq, Slide-seqV2, Stereo-seq	5 μm (Visium), 10 μm (Slide-seq), <1 μm (Stereo-seq)	Whole-transcriptome analysis; high coverage; spatial barcodes on slides or beads ^[18,19]
Probe-based methods	GeoMx DSP, HybISS, Molecular Cartography	10–100 μm ROI	Detects pre-selected gene panels; good for FFPE samples; region-specific targeting ^[18,20]
Imaging based methods	MERFISH, seqFISH+, STARmap, FISSEQ, ISS	Subcellular (~0.1–1 μm)	Visualizes transcripts in situ; excellent spatial detail; multiplexing capability, ^[18,6]
Image guided scRNA sequencing methods	NICHE-seq, LCM + scRNA-seq, GeoMX + scRNA-seq	Single cell	Combines spatial selection (via imaging) with high-depth scRNA-seq ^[18,21]

Procedure (Identifying TME using ST)

Figure 1: Procedure of ST.

a. Extract tissue section

Start by mounting a small piece of tumour tissue on a slide, usually frozen or formalin-fixed paraffin-embedded (FFPE) especially in 10x genomics visium.^[22,16]

b. Capture spatial gene expression

For preserving spatial context, use either imaging-based ST (in situ hybridization/sequencing) or next-generation sequencing (NGS)-based ST (incorporating spatial barcodes into transcripts).^[22] This creates a gene-expression matrix that is spatially resolved and associated with the tissue picture.^[6]

c. Identify the cell types

Allocate different cell types (tumour cells, immune cells, stroma) to each spatial location or pixel by using spatial patterns. It reveals the cellular constitution of specific areas.^[21]

d. Mapping the TME

Using histology and expression patterns, visually divide the tissue into biologically significant areas such as the tumour core, invasive boundary, stromal/immune-rich zones, etc.^[23]

e. Identify key genes & spatial patterns

Identification of genes and expression modules enriched in specific TME zones can be achieved using spatially varying gene identification and differential expression analysis.^[23]

f. Map cell interactions

Assess co-localization, cell-cell communication, and higher-order spatial markers such as immunological areas, tumor-stromal interfaces, and ligand-receptor interactions by using ST.^[8,24]

g. Multi-omic integration

For improving cellular and molecular resolution, combine ST with spatial proteomic technologies (e.g., GeoMx DSP, CODEX), single-cell transcriptomics (scRNA-seq), or multi-omics.^[25]

h. Visualize & interpret the results

To see the organisation of TME components, overlay tissue pictures with gene expression and cell type maps. Analyse spatial interactions with an emphasis on tumour heterogeneity, immunotherapy biomarkers, or microenvironmental gradients.^[6]

Insights gained from Spatial transcriptomics on TME

Table 2: Insights obtained using ST in various cancer types.

Type of cancer	Study	Technique	TME components identified
Colorectal cancer	Integrative single cell & ST	Visium ST + scRNA-seq integration	B cells, T cells, NK cells, monocytes, mast cells, fibroblasts, endothelial cells, malignant epithelial cells ^[26]
Colorectal cancer	Spatial cell	10x Genomics Visium mapped to scRNA-seq signatures	Multiple immune subsets (T/B/NK/monocytes), stromal fibroblasts, endothelial cells; spatial malignant programs ^[27]
Prognostic CRC niches (Colorectal cancer)	Spatial deconvolution	10x Genomics Visium + computational deconvolution	Reactive vs suppressed immune populations (T cells, myeloid), CAFs, vascular cells ^[28]
Breast cancer	Single cell & ST	10x Genomics Visium combined with scRNA-seq	Tumor epithelial cells, myeloid cells, T/B lymphocytes, CAFs, endothelial & adipose/stroma ^[29]
Lung cancer	Early lung adenocarcinoma profiling	10x Genomics Visium + scRNA-seq integration	AT2-like/tumor epithelial cells, macrophage subtypes, T cells, endothelial niches ^[30]
Colorectal cancer	Visium HD profiling (FFPE)	10x Genomics Visium HD (high definition)	Tumor cells, CAF subpopulations, T/NK/B cells, endothelial cells (single-cell scale) ^[31]
Triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC)	Cohort	10x Genomics Visium (cohort profiling)	T cells, macrophages, B cells; immune-rich vs immune-cold stromal zones ^[32]
NSCLC (non-small cell lung cancer)	Spatial mapping	10x Genomics Visium combined with scRNA-seq	Macrophage subtypes, T and B lymphocytes, endothelial cells, stromal fibroblasts ^[33]
Triple-negative breast cancer	ST across patient cohort	Multiple ST platforms (Visium examples)	Lymphoid/myeloid immune cells, fibroblasts, vasculature recurring across cancers ^[34]
Oral squamous carcinoma	iCAF profiling	10x Genomics Visium with scRNA-seq validation	iCAFs and other CAF subtypes, macrophages, suppressive myeloid cells ^[35]
Glioblastoma	Tumor cell state spatial segregation	10x Genomics Visium mapped to scRNA clusters	Distinct tumor cell states and local T/myeloid and stromal cells occupying zones ^[36]
LUAD	LUAD progression via ST	Visium ST combined with scRNA-seq	Tumor epithelial subpopulations, macrophages, endothelial cells, T cell niches ^[37]

SCLC	SCLC macrophage reprogramming	10x Genomics Visium + complementary assays	Reprogrammed tumor-associated macrophages, epithelial tumor cells, other immune cells ^[38]
Preneoplastic breast cancer	Mammary epithelial differentiation changes	10x Genomics Visium examples + scRNA references	Altered epithelial cells, localized immune shifts, stromal fibroblast remodeling ^[39]
Colorectal cancer	Image-inferred ST markers (CRC validation)	10x Genomics Visium used to validate histology-derived markers	Tumor epithelium, immune hotspots, stromal regions validated by ST ^[40]
Endometrial carcinoma	ST, scRNA	10x Genomics Visium integrated with scRNA-seq	Epithelial cells, endothelial cells, fibroblasts, immune cells ^[41]
Neck carcinoma	ST, scRNA, IHC	10x Genomics Visium	Tcells, macrophages, dendritic cells ^[42]
Renal carcinoma	ST, scRNA	10x Genomics Visium	T cells, fibroblasts, endothelial cells, macrophages ^[43]
Osteocarcinoma	ST, scRNA	10x Genomics Visium	TAMs, fibroblasts, endothelial cells ^[44]
Hepatocellular carcinoma	ST, scRNA	10x Genomics Visium	CAFs, MGAT 1, endothelial cells ^[45]
Pancreatic adenocarcinoma	ST, scRNA	10x Genomics Visium	CAFs, CD10+, KLF4, TIAM1, immune cells ^[46]
Leptomeningeal disease (LMD)	ST, scRNA	10x Genomics Visium	TAFs, meningeal stromal cells ^[47]

Challenges

- i. Identifying closely neighbouring cell types can be difficult due to spot size or platform limitations.^[48]
- ii. The diversified and heterogeneous cell populations found in tumour microenvironments make it more difficult to precisely identify and map particular cell types in space.^[3]
- iii. Limited ability to detect unusual or low-abundance transcripts due to a lower sensitivity of ST than single-cell RNA-seq.^[49]
- iv. Errors in sampling handling and analysis can compromise the accuracy of spatial data and RNA integrity.^[50]
- v. Spatial pattern analysis needs advanced technology and knowledge that are still being developed.^[51]

Advancements

- i. Methods like as Stereo-seq and Slide-seq increase resolution to almost single-cell or subcellular levels.^[49]

- ii. Thousands of genes can be detected per spot thanks to new technologies and methods, increasing the extent of the data.^[48]
- iii. Emergence of sophisticated pipelines and algorithms for the analysis, deconvolution, and visualisation of spatial data.^[51]
- iv. Emergence of multimodal spatial omics techniques that integrate proteomics, epigenomics, and transcriptomics for thorough tissue studies.^[52]
- v. Neuroscience, immunology, developmental biology, and cancer biology all use spatial transcriptomics to uncover disease processes, cell interactions, and tissue heterogeneity.^[53]

Applications

- i. In order to develop individualised treatment plans, ST has been crucial in revealing the intricate structures of tumours and locating spatially controlled biomarkers.^[22]
- ii. Researchers can examine the relationship between gene expression and neuronal activity and connectivity by maintaining the spatial context, which helps them understand neurological illnesses.^[18]
- iii. Useful to identify treatment targets and find biomarkers in tumor tissues.^[54]
- iv. Reveals various cancer cell types and their surroundings through the spatial mapping of tumour heterogeneity.^[53]
- v. Evaluates how tumours evolve spatially in response to treatments, directing the creation of combination and targeted therapies.^[55]
- vi. Enables extensive spatial profiling of immune cells, fibroblasts, and other stromal components that interact with tumour cells and examines the mechanisms of medication resistance and tumour relapse.^[21]

ST in treatment selection:

Patient Selection for Immunotherapy: Tumor immune-rich and immune-poor areas are identified using spatial transcriptomics. By displaying the real locations of immune cells and PD-L1 (Programmed Death-Ligand 1) in the tissue, this aids in identifying which patients are most likely to react to immune checkpoint inhibitors.^[29]

CONCLUSION

Spatial transcriptomics has emerged as a valuable tool for deciphering the complex cellular structure and molecular connections found in the tumor microenvironment. ST provides incomparable insights into how various cell populations contribute to tumor growth,

immunological evasion, and treatment resistance by retaining spatial context as well as gene expression profiles. Despite substantial developments in technology and analytical approaches, issues such as poor resolution, data integration complexity, and high prices must be addressed. Continued developments in spatial resolution, multi-omics integration, and computational techniques provide promise for overcoming these limits. The increased use of spatial transcriptomics in oncology research is resulting in a better knowledge of TME heterogeneity, which can help build more precise and effective cancer treatments. Finally, using ST to decipher the TME will improve tailored treatment strategies and patient outcomes.

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